

Adoption of Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) policy in marketing

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Abstract

Rapid development of mobile technologies establishes a solid framework for the deployment of mobile hardware in several aspects of entrepreneurship. There is a continuous and enhancement demand for mobile applications and enterprises' daily office work gradually expand from PC to mobile terminals realizing the Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) policy. Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) as one of important mobile office modes has received the academia's extensive attention in recent years.

Contemporary working methods deploy BYOD in several phases and stages such as offline mobile office, online mobile office, and intelligent mobile office. Towards this direction BYOD has been introduced in several sectors such as education, health, office mode, etc.

The purpose of the specific paper is to introduce a concept of BYOD policy in marketing based on high-end technological IT solutions. Through this research work a system framework will be defined aiming to combine technological trends with wireless marketing strategies integrating BYOD features.

Keywords: *Bring Your Own Device, Marketing, Mobile Signage*

1 Introduction

Mobile communication is a major technology growing rapidly and having a great market potential. It is also well known that Internet technology is a key and major technology that grows rapidly with significant market potential. It is obvious that Mobile Internet is also explosively growing resulting to significant changes and radical changes to several industries in recent years. As the Cisco's 2016 global mobile data traffic forecast report release mentions that almost half a billion (429 million) mobile devices and connections were added in 2016. Smartphones accounted for most of that growth, followed by M2M modules. Global mobile devices and connections in 2016 grew to 8.0 billion, up from 7.6 billion in 2015. Globally, smart devices represented 46 percent of the total mobile devices and connections in 2016; they accounted for 89 percent of the mobile data traffic. ("smart devices" refers to mobile connections that have advanced multimedia/computing capabilities with a minimum of 3G connectivity.) [1].

Based on this it is easy to understand that the future of technology will be strongly related to mobile technology.

The expansion of technological features of mobile devices has resulted to significant increase and use of mobile applications and Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) as one of important mobile office modes has received the academia's extensive attention in recent years [2].

Based on the entrepreneurial exploitation in literature there are different perspectives such as Morrow B et al [3] mentioning that Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) is a policy for employees allowing them to bring their own machines (laptops, tablets, smart phones and other mobile devices) to their work. Although employees use their own devices, they have access rights to enterprise's internal information and they can use enterprise's licensed applications. Another perspective comes from Thomson G [4] showing the three stages of mobile office: offline, online and intelligent. Furthermore, [7] reports the phenomenon of extensive use of personal devices for work in enterprises. A rather different perspective comes from the use in the field of education, Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) is also widely used in the specific field, and has become a new education information service mode in recent years [5].

2. Main Concept of BYOD in Marketing

Based on the key findings of mobile smartphone usage and the penetration rate of smartphones in our everyday lives a key question arises for marketing Managers "How do I take advantage of smartphone to use it in MARKETING". The answer to this is to integrate information technology with Marketing and develop solutions

that will deliver content to the smartphone of the visitor / customer based on the principles of proximity marketing [6].

It is well known that BYOD concept has been adopted by several organisations allowing their employees to work with their own devices [7]. BYOD's benefits are clear: employees are more familiar and satisfied with using their own device(s), and employers save money by not having to pay for high-priced devices and data plans. Companies' goals with BYOD are to increase the flexibility, convenience, and portability of devices that cater to their employees' workflows, which increases productivity and morale [7].

However there are some initiatives which are trying to integrate the concept of the smartphone usage and marketing such as [8] aiming to design integrated systems for marketing allowing the end user to access the marketing services and information with their own smartphone without having to install any mobile application or to access internet. They only have to connect to a free Wi-Fi near them.

So, the proposal is to develop the specific concept aiming to develop solutions that will allow the end user to access information on his own smartphone without having to install on the specific device any mobile application. It is well known that smartphones and their associated apps are useful in all forms of tourism travel arrangements and tourists are clearly depended on their smartphone and the information they can retrieve on their personal device [9]. Nowadays SMART CITIES and SMART PLACES are an important trend resulting to SMART TOURIST DESTINATIONS [10].

The overall idea and the main concept of applying contemporary information technology to marketing are setting the background to develop solutions that will establish the vaulting horse for smart solutions aiming to facilitate the use of smartphones in marketing. Tourism seems to lead the way towards this direction and soon other sectors will also incorporate the BYOD concept.

3. New BYOD Framework and proposed solution

The basis for the success of the specific BYOD concept on marketing is established on the fact that access to information and to services is not provided by a mobile application. The simplest solution is to provide the information to the end user through a mini-site. Mini sites are easy to be developed and based on the fact that modern smartphones have features equal to a PC, a programmer is able to develop a mini site with the all the functionalities of a contemporary site and smartphones are able to access these mini sites without problems.

The aforementioned concept can be deployed with a system solution proposed in [8] resolving the most important issue of the technological barrier of smartphones, which is the difficulty to access content stored on another device, which can be accessed by local WiFi.

The technological solution of [12] paves the way to marketing success. Of course the specific development is at early stage and lots of work needs to be done for the proper development and deployment of the technological breakthrough towards marketing deployment.

4. Future Work

BYOD is a successful trend of modern generation. Especially in business organization and education seems to penetrate the majority of cases. However, the dependency of persons from their smartphones and the fact that smartphone has become the most important personal device is guiding marketing professionals and IT people to collaborate and develop marketing solutions based on the BYOD concept.

The specific proposed concept is rather new in the field of contemporary proximity marketing and requires several steps in order to mature as solution with high quality standards able to be integrated in the real world. The team is already working on a specific project idea to publish in the near future an integrated Proximity Marketing BYOD business solution.

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